

WORKING IN THE ERA OF AI: BALANCING AI INTEGRATION AND EMPLOYEE WELL-BEING ACROSS CONTEXTS AND CULTURES

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Abstract

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in workplaces has garnered significant attention in recent years, with statistics indicating a notable rise in AI adoption across various economic sectors. The implications of AI integration for employment remain a subject of debate, with conflicting perspectives on its potential impact on unemployment rates. Moreover, there is uncertainty regarding whether AI adoption ultimately yields positive or negative outcomes for employee well-being and mental health. To better understand the multifaceted role of AI in employee well-being, this paper reviews 12 academic articles spanning diverse contexts, demographic characteristics, and cultural settings. Through this review, potential solutions to workplace challenges arising from AI integration are identified, highlighting the need for strategic approaches to address potential negative impacts on employee well-being, including inducing job insecurity, stress, and low job engagement. Ultimately, this review underscores the complexity of the relationship between AI and employees in the workplace, emphasizing the importance of further research to elucidate this dynamic and inform future strategies for mitigating potential adverse effects.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, technology, workplace, employee well-being, mental health, job insecurity, demographics, culture, symbiotic relationship, policy recommendations

1. INTRODUCTION

According to Moore (2019)'s definition, "AI 'refers to systems that display intelligent behavior by analyzing their environment and taking actions—with some degree of autonomy—to achieve specific goals.'" From facilitating information retrieval to transforming the nature of work itself, AI has become increasingly pervasive in our daily lives. The most recent Business Trends and Outlook Survey (BTOS), conducted between October 23 and November 5, 2023 revealed that approximately 3.9% of businesses currently employ AI in their operations, with substantial variations observed among different sectors. Notably, the Information sector reported a significantly higher rate of AI usage at 13.8%, followed closely by the Professional, Scientific, and Technical Services sector at 9.1%. Although these adoption rates may appear modest, projections suggest a rapid escalation, with estimates indicating a potential increase to 21.8% (Information Sector) and 15.2% (Professional, Scientific and Technical Services) in just six months (Breux & Dinlersoz, 2023). The burgeoning presence of AI in workplaces is further underscored by significant investments made by tech giants such as Microsoft and Google, reflecting a broader trend of ongoing investments and advancements in AI technologies (Gruetzemacher & Lee, 2020). As AI continues to

permeate various facets of organizational functioning, ranging from machine learning to chatbots and HR processes, understanding its implications for the workforce becomes increasingly crucial. This paper aims to explore the rising integration of AI across diverse departments of the occupational field, examining its impact on employee well-being and mental health, and identifying potential strategies to address associated challenges.

Over the past decade, significant advancements in artificial intelligence (AI), particularly in machine learning and deep learning, have sparked debates about their limits while also indicating substantial impacts on labor markets. Notably, deep learning systems, which emulate the human brain's data processing, have surpassed human-level performance in tasks such as image classification, game-playing, and text generation. Deep learning has achieved remarkable success in areas such as computer vision, reinforcement learning, and natural language processing (NLP), potentially reshaping labor dynamics reliant on human interaction through language. While limitations still exist in the field of AI, practitioners anticipate that automation will lead to considerable labor displacement over the coming decades, with some statistical predictions exceeding 90% of labor being displaced. Moreover, considering the recent advancement of OpenAI, an artificial intelligence research laboratory, practitioners' forecasts suggest that it is even possible for generative AI to accelerate the labor displacement phenomenon in less than a decade (Gruetzemacher et al., 2020).

However, not all experts agree that AI integration will significantly impact employment rates in the labor market. Conflicting arguments exist regarding the impact of AI integration on unemployment rates in labor markets. For example, Mutascu and Hegerty (2023) utilized an artificial neuron network (ANN) tool to predict different countries' unemployment rates based on a set of characteristics, with AI being a prominent factor. They found that AI does not play a crucial role in unemployment, suggesting that adaptive adjustments in AI use in the workplace may minimize job replacement effects. They further suggested that developed countries need cohesive measures to support the labor market and approach economic expansion by creating new jobs (Mutascu & Hegerty, 2023). The ambiguous findings imply the need for further investigation into the relationship between AI and employment. The discrepancy in arguments may stem from differences in study samples, with the first study incorporating forecasts from professional AI practitioners, while the second study utilizes cross-cultural data from 23 countries. Whether the threat of AI replacing workers and leading to unemployment is supported in the evidence, concerns persist regarding its impact on employee well-being. According to estimates by Oxford researchers Frey and Osborne (2013), nearly half of today's jobs in the United States could become susceptible to automation within the next two decades, leading to significant workforce upheaval and potential job obsolescence (McClure, 2018). This looming threat of automation adds an additional layer of stress to an already challenging economic landscape, particularly as the U.S. economy grapples with high unemployment rates and widespread job insecurity. Furthermore, as AI becomes increasingly integrated into workplaces, important questions regarding occupational safety and health (OSH) emerge, highlighting the need for comprehensive assessments of the potential risks and benefits associated with AI adoption. Amidst these uncertainties, mental health considerations become paramount, as employees navigate the evolving nature of work and contend with the psychological impacts of job insecurity and technological disruption. Therefore, this paper strives to better understand the relationship between AI and employee well-being through the review of 12 empirical articles sharing evidence from national and international perspectives, to better understand not only how AI may influence employee well-being, but who it might impact the most. The following research question guides this review: *How does the increasing integration of artificial intelligence into workplaces impact the psychological well-being of employees across different populations and occupations? Does culture matter?*

2. PSYCHOLOGICAL IMPACT OF AI INTEGRATION IN THE WORKPLACE

While AI's effect on the labor market remains an open question, AI's powerful potential and its imminent threat can have psychological consequences for workers. Several studies provide evidence that AI integration in the workplace elicits diverse impacts on employees' psychological well-being. A national survey conducted by Nazareno and Schiff in 2021 examined AI's effect on the mental health of employees across four dimensions: job satisfaction, stress, job insecurity, and overall health. Their findings revealed that the impact of AI integration on employee well-being changes over time. Initially, stress levels decreased during the introduction of AI, but they increased over time (Nazareno & Schiff, 2021). The initial reduction in stress can be attributed to AI and automation significantly enhancing employee productivity by handling repetitive and complex tasks that consume extensive time and effort. However, as employees directly

experience AI's high capabilities in the workplace, they may start to lose self-efficacy, leading to decreased job satisfaction, increased stress, and heightened job insecurity.

Furthermore, an online survey questionnaire conducted by Braganza et al. (2021) examined similar effects across four domains: AI adoption, psychological contract, job engagement, and job satisfaction. They discovered that AI adoption weakens the positive relationship between psychological contract and job engagement, suggesting that AI adoption negatively impacts job engagement by creating uncertainty at work. Job engagement is vital to overall organizational prosperity, as more engaged employees are likely to trust the organization they work for. Considering this fact, Braganza et al. highlighted the necessity of developing new social contracts to ensure employees feel secure in their positions and are more engaged with their work (Braganza et al., 2021). This underscores the responsibility of employers to seek for a balance between AI and human employees, fostering a harmonious and productive workplace where AI serves as an opportunity rather than a threat. Additionally, Nazareno and Schiff (2021) noted that "these technologies influence and are influenced by job content and context, as well as by broader socio-technical and economic factors" (Nazareno & Schiff, 2021). This implies that the impact of AI on employee well-being is complex and multifaceted, influenced by various factors within the work environment and broader societal dynamics.

2.1. Job Contents

In contemporary workplaces, AI has become pervasive across diverse functions, with its emergence even in supervisory and managerial roles raising significant concerns regarding privacy and compliance. While AI is a product of human innovation, its adoption as a managerial authority in the workplace disrupts the conventional hierarchical relationship. Operating through micro-management techniques that intimately monitor and record employee productivity, AI supervisors foster an environment devoid of privacy and characterized by strict compliance enforcement. This trend of AI integration into HR decision-making processes across diverse workplaces exacerbates Occupational Safety and Health (OSH) risks for employees. Therefore, it's imperative to explore the ethical implications, such as the potential for bias in AI decision-making and the psychological impact on employees subjected to intensive monitoring (Moore, 2019).

Furthermore, in the discourse surrounding the impact of AI across various job contents, Garnett (2018) asserts that workplace AI disproportionately benefits high-skilled job workers while presenting threats to those in low-skilled positions, suggesting a significant trust gap between AI and low-skilled workers (Zirar et al., 2023). However, contrary to Garnett's predictions, a national survey by Yam et al. (2023) reveals that AI adoption induces job insecurity among employees in intellectually demanding roles as well. These roles encompass tasks requiring advanced analytical skills and creative abilities. The study also examines the variability of AI exposure and its correlation with job insecurity. By measuring the levels of AI prevalence across 50 states in the United States and individuals' sense of job insecurity, they found that employees generally feel insecure about robot exposure in their workplace, leading to psychological costs such as burnout and workplace incivility. (Yam et al., 2023). This finding highlights the broad impact of AI integration on employee well-being across a wide variety of job contents, challenging previous assumptions about its effects primarily on low-skilled jobs. The revelation that AI adoption induces job insecurity among employees in intellectually demanding roles underscores the need for a comprehensive understanding of the dynamics at play in AI-enabled workplaces.

2.2. Demographics

Several scholars have further investigated the kinds of environments and characteristics that may influence wellbeing from AI integration. The Chapman Survey of American Fears, Wave 2 (CSAF) conducted by McClure in 2018 identified technophobes in different demographic groups in the United States, including gender, age, race, residence in metropolitan areas, income, and education. They found that females, non-White minorities, and individuals with lower levels of education are more likely to fear the development of AI technologies, potentially leading to negative effects on mental health due to concerns about unemployment and financial insecurity. Particularly noteworthy is the consistent reporting of fear among women compared to men (McClure, 2018). This gender discrepancy may result from societal perceptions that undervalue women's capabilities, fostering feelings of insecurity in the workplace among women. Although AI may inherently embody masculine values, it is more likely that societal contexts influence women's perceptions rather than AI technologies themselves. At the same time research has shown that AI does generate gender-

biased content, particularly related to leadership in the workplace (Newstead et al., 2023).

3. CROSS-CULTURAL ANALYSIS

3.1. South Korea and the United States

Based on the findings presented in the preceding section, it is evident that the impact of AI integration in the workplace on employee well-being varies by demographic characteristics at the national level. Consequently, it is worthwhile to explore these differences in cross-cultural contexts that differ in workplace environments and norms, specifically East Asian cultures and Western cultures (e.g. Adler, 2003). A national survey conducted in South Korea by Lee et al. (2022) examined employees' qualitative job insecurity resulting from AI integration in the workplace. Their findings revealed a positive association between tech-related changes and employees' reports of job insecurity, indicating that increased AI integration led to heightened anxiety about the potential threat to their jobs (Lee et al., 2022). This suggests that the psychological impacts of AI on employees in the workplace were also visible in South Korea.

A cluster analysis conducted by Yang and Kim in 2023, utilizing patents in South Korea, identified highly vulnerable occupations to AI replacement based on their characteristics and spatial distribution. The study discovered the top 10 vulnerable occupations to AI integration, including life science technicians (excluding Medical), various major groups of professionals and technicians, associate professionals, and economists. These occupations share a commonality in that their tasks involve the use of existing technologies or identifying data patterns rather than generating new creations. This implies that tasks requiring creativity and complexity based on substantial past experience are more resistant to transformation into AI tasks. Furthermore, the study examined the spatial distribution of this phenomenon, concluding that there are differences in impacts of AI between capital and non-capital areas of Korea due to significantly higher digital intensity levels in the capital areas. (Yang & Kim, 2023). Although regional differences were not evident in the studies focusing on the impacts of AI in the U.S., similar effects are anticipated in Western cultures, where economic disparities clearly exist.

3.2. The East and the West

The evidence directly comparing AI integration and employee well-being across cultural contexts is limited, however there is emerging work. In a broader examination of cultural differences between East and West, a study by Mantello et al. (2023) explored the effects of socio-demographic and cross-cultural factors on the impact of AI integration in the workplace. Their findings revealed intriguing patterns, with people from economically less developed regions, such as Africa, Oceania, and Central Asia, exhibiting less concern for AI-enabled management compared to those from more economically developed regions like Europe and Northern America. Notably, economically developed regions in East Asia, including Japan, South Korea, and China, demonstrated a lesser degree of anxiety toward AI-enabled HR management, with a significant percentage expressing a more accepting attitude. This phenomenon may be attributed to the influence of Confucianism, which prioritizes collectivism over individualism, leading to greater acceptance of intervention by higher authority seen as moral guidance. Conversely, a substantial majority of individuals from European and Northern American regions express a worried attitude toward being managed by AI (Mantello et al., 2023). The apprehension observed among individuals from European and Northern American regions may be linked to a cultural inclination toward valuing autonomy and individual agency in decision-making processes. In these cultures, there is a strong emphasis on personal freedom and the ability to make independent choices without external interference. Therefore, the prospect of AI taking on managerial roles and making decisions on behalf of individuals may be perceived as a threat to their autonomy and sense of control over their work environment. In the end, these findings underscore the importance of cultural factors, particularly the distinction between collectivist and individualist values, in shaping perceptions of AI integration in the workplace.

4. DISCUSSION

The psychological impact of AI integration in the workplace is multifaceted and varies across job contents, demographics, and cultural contexts. Studies have shown that AI integration elicits diverse effects on employees' psychological well-being, including changes in job satisfaction, stress levels, and overall job engagement. While initial reductions in stress may occur during the introduction of AI due to enhanced productivity, prolonged exposure to AI in the workplace can lead to increased stress, decreased job satisfaction, and heightened job insecurity. Additionally, AI adoption has been found to weaken the positive

relationship between psychological contract and job engagement, contributing to increased uncertainty at work. The impact of AI employee well-being for different job contents is nuanced, challenging previous assumptions about its effects primarily on low-skilled jobs and suggesting its equivalent effects on high-skilled jobs. Demographic factors such as gender, age, and education level also play a role in shaping perceptions of AI, with women and individuals from less economically developed regions expressing greater fear and anxiety about AI integration. Cultural differences further influence attitudes toward AI, with collectivist cultures exhibiting greater acceptance of AI-enabled management compared to individualist cultures. Overall, these findings highlight the complex interplay between AI integration, psychological well-being, and cultural factors in the workplace, emphasizing the need for comprehensive approaches to address the psychological consequences of AI adoption.

4.1. Lack of Definitive Solutions to Potential Negative Impacts of AI

While numerous studies have highlighted the significant impacts of AI integration on employees' mental health, they also underscore the absence of definitive solutions to this phenomenon. The suggested remedies primarily revolve around internally adoptable strategies aimed at mitigating the negative effects. For instance, Nazareno and Schiff (2021) advocate for employers to carefully consider various factors when integrating AI into the workplace, with the goal of reducing adverse impacts on employees' mental well-being and fostering a positive work environment. Similarly, Yam et al. (2023) propose the self-affirmation method as a potential approach to counteracting the negative effects of AI exposure. This method emphasizes employees affirming their self-worth and abilities to cope with the psychological costs associated with AI integration. However, the effectiveness of self-affirmation may vary across individuals, with those with low-self-esteem potentially struggling to cope with job insecurity through this method. Despite these proposed solutions, it is evident that addressing the complex interplay between AI integration and employee mental health requires further exploration. Future research should aim to delve deeper into the underlying mechanisms driving these impacts and explore additional strategies, both internal and external, to effectively mitigate the negative consequences and promote employee well-being in AI-enabled workplaces.

Unfortunately, solutions remain inconclusive in cross-cultural analyses. For instance, Kim et al. (2024) survey, conducted over three distinct periods, explored how personal capabilities in AI usage can mitigate the detrimental impact of job insecurity caused by AI in the workplace. They found that "when an employee's self-efficacy in AI usage was high, job insecurity had a reduced harmful influence on psychological safety" (Kim et al., 2024). This implies that employees' confidence in their ability to use AI may help alleviate the negative impacts of job insecurity on their psychological well-being. Additionally, according to Yang and Kim (2023), given the varying impact of AI varies across different occupations and spatial distributions, areas in which many workers with high vulnerability to AI, especially local industries, need to "create new occupations and form a new task structure." This underscores the importance of identifying the technological characteristics of AI in different regional conditions to attract suitable industries and human resources, thus maximizing economic productivity. Furthermore, Mantello et al. (2023) propose that organizational approaches to AI adoption should consider cultural nuances to ensure effective implementation and mitigate potential negative impacts on employee well-being. This highlights the need for cross-cultural sensitivity in designing AI-enabled management systems to foster acceptance and promote a supportive work environment across diverse cultural contexts.

4.2. The Possibility and Importance of a Coexistence between AI and Human Employees

The coexistence of AI and human employees in the workplace signifies a symbiotic relationship, wherein each side complements the other's strengths and weaknesses. While AI enhances tasks by providing precision in number processing and pattern recognition, empowering employees to focus on intricate decision-making and critical analysis, it encounters limitations in areas such as physical object handling and empathetic understanding (Zirar et al., 2023). For example, imagine a customer service scenario where AI chatbots efficiently handle routine inquiries but struggle to grasp the nuanced emotions of frustrated customers. The deficiency in empathetic understanding, a fundamental human trait, underscores the importance of human involvement in instructing AI and contributing feasible yet effective plans to enhance overall productivity. Consequently, addressing how organizations can bridge these gaps through human-AI collaboration would enhance the analysis and shed light on the implications for workplace dynamics and employee well-being. Despite assertions of AI's superior capabilities across diverse domains, the symbiotic coexistence of AI and human employees remains indispensable until AI achieves the ultimate "perfection"

(Zirar et al., 2023). For this reason, the central focus of addressing these challenges should shift from the technology itself to its appropriate implementation within workplace contexts.

5. CONCLUSION

Relying on employees to self-fund their upskilling and reskilling efforts in response to the increasing integration of AI in the workplace can yield negative consequences for both employers and employees, impacting work engagement, employee health, and work/nonwork conflicts. Therefore, it is imperative for employers to prioritize the adoption of AI in the workplace and invest in funding for employee development to foster a harmonious and productive work environment. Moreover, policymakers must play a crucial role by formulating comprehensive guidelines and adaptive regulations concerning AI usage in workplaces. These measures should aim to mitigate the job replacement effects of AI and alleviate its negative impact on employees' psychological well-being. Particularly in developed countries, where the influence of AI integration is most pronounced, policymakers should establish coherent measures to attract foreign direct investments that support job creation and economic growth. This will provide employees in industries vulnerable to AI replacement with alternative avenues to regain economic stability. Additionally, in light of the varying impacts of AI across different occupations and spatial distributions, it is essential for policymakers to facilitate the creation of new occupations and the restructuring of task structures, especially in local industries with high vulnerability to AI. While there are limitations to job creation in labor markets, efforts should be made to support employees in developing confidence in utilizing AI. This can help mitigate the negative impacts of job insecurity on their psychological well-being, ultimately fostering a more resilient workforce in the face of AI integration.

In light of the limited solutions offered for addressing the potential negative impacts of AI integration in workplaces, future research should delve into several key areas to uncover missing pieces of this complex phenomenon. Firstly, employing a qualitative approach could be beneficial in analyzing the reasons why certain occupations are more vulnerable to AI displacement, as well as the adaptive processes employees undertake to navigate technological changes in their roles. This qualitative inquiry can potentially address questions raised by McClure (2018)'s study regarding the extent to which AI reflects masculine values in its design and interfaces. By exploring these gender biases, researchers can better understand how different demographic groups perceive and interact with AI systems. Furthermore, future research should assess the effectiveness of interventions such as self-affirmation techniques in diverse workplace settings to determine their efficacy in mitigating the negative consequences of AI integration on employee well-being. In the event that these techniques prove ineffective, alternative psychological strategies should be explored to address the challenges posed by AI integration in the workplace. Lastly, studying the trends and relationships of international knowledge exchange regarding AI integration could provide valuable insights into global patterns and strategies for managing its impact on the workforce. By addressing these research gaps, scholars can contribute to developing more definitive solutions that promote employee adoption to the evolving AI landscape while safeguarding their psychological health and overall well-being.

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